

IMPROVING RELATIONS BETWEEN PARTICIPANTS IN THE INVESTMENT AND CONSTRUCTION PROCESS

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Abstract. *The purpose of the article is to optimize the construction time, which is currently considered one of the most complex and controversial problems in the investment and construction sector. The reduction of construction time is primarily a result of the economic interest of participants in the investment and construction process. The source of economic interest of construction participants is the benefit of each of them, that is, the service of the customer, project organization, general construction organization. An important area of improvement in the rationing of construction terms is the further development of elements of economic and contract construction methods.*

Keywords: *construction duration, production method, construction participants, economic effect.*

Introduction. The development of the construction industry is directly related to the improvement of the regulatory and technical framework, which forms the basis for evaluating the effectiveness of the investment and construction process as a whole. In this regard, Development Strategy of New Uzbekistan for 2022-2026 sets the goal of "...Improving technical regulation in the construction sector" [1]. Currently, in the construction industry, there are cases of reducing the quality of commissioned facilities, overstating the cost of construction work and unreasonably increasing the construction time. One of the systemic reasons for these shortcomings is a significant lag in updating the technical regulation of urban development activities [2]. In particular, this applies to the duration of the investment and construction process in general and the norms for the duration of construction of objects. Rationing the duration of construction should have a solid methodological basis, extensive information practice and take into account the possibility of using modern methods and technologies of construction production. The country's leadership is taking active measures to improve technical regulation in construction [3]. Organizational measures should be supported by scientific and methodological developments that contribute to the justification of regulatory and technical requirements. One of the most relevant areas of improvement of technical regulation is the improvement of methods and tools for improving the investment and construction process.

Research methodology. Systematic approach, abstract-logical thinking, grouping, comparison, factor analysis, selective observation methods were used in the research process.

Research results. As it is known, the creation of construction products provides for the fulfillment of a triune task, which characterizes the fulfillment of the following interrelated requirements: the implementation of the project with the necessary level of quality, within the allocated investment volumes and within the established time frame. At the same time, the requirement to implement the project on time has a decisive impact on the other two elements, that is, on the quality and final cost of the construction object.

The investment and construction process are an ordering of actions to achieve investment goals that ensure the efficiency of all construction participants. The full cycle of the investment and construction process includes the following stages: setting investment goals and allocating the necessary funds, pre-project work, design of construction objects, organization of construction (logistics, construction work, installation of technological equipment, running-in of components of the object, operation).

The main factor influencing the efficiency of the investment and construction process is the distribution of responsibility between construction participants. The model of distribution of responsibility in each investment project is called the method of organization of construction. There are many different ways to organize construction. At the same time, we can distinguish two extreme opposite points of construction methods: economic method and contract method.

In the economic way of organizing construction, all powers and responsibilities are concentrated on the investor, who is also the developer, that is, the owner of the land plot on which construction is planned. The investor, due to its isolation, performs the functions of a customer, design, construction and maintenance organization. All work is carried out by the forces and means of existing enterprises or organizations.

The economic method in its pure form is rare. Usually, large industrial enterprises use it for updating fixed assets, technical re-equipment, and sometimes for the reconstruction of individual production facilities.

The advantages of the economic method of construction include full satisfaction of the investor's requirements, independent setting of construction deadlines, flexible provision of construction resources, consistency of all stages of the investment and construction cycle. The disadvantages of this method are the low qualification of performers and, as a rule, the low quality of the finished object, the increase in the cost of construction, and a decrease in the effectiveness of actions at the stages of the investment and construction process.

The contract method of production is the opposite of the economic method. In it, all stages of the investment and construction process are distributed among independent economic entities that interact on the basis of contractual relations. For example, an investor is bound by a contract with a customer, who in turn has a contract with a project and general contractor organization. Similarly, relationships with resource suppliers, subcontractors, supervisors, and credit institutions are also built on a contractual basis. Each construction participant has its own material interest and obligations under the contracts.

The undoubted advantages of the contract construction method are high competence of construction participants, mutual control over the fulfillment of contractual obligations, and ensuring construction within the required time frame within the limits of investment volumes. In addition, with the contract construction method, market relations are manifested in the investment and construction process.

The disadvantage of the contracting method is the bureaucratization of relations between construction participants, the complexity of resolving disputes, and the discrepancy between the economic interests of each participant and the overall goals of the investment project. It should be noted that to overcome these shortcomings, construction participants use various methods of cooperation, for example: combining the functions of the customer and the developer, creating design and construction associations, etc.

The total duration of an investment project is defined as the sum of the durations of all stages. At the same time, the investor's interests presuppose determining the optimal (shortest from an organizational and technical point of view) period for the implementation of an investment project, which implies combining work on individual stages of the project.

Consequently, reducing the duration of the investment and construction process includes several areas: speeding up the development of a feasibility study for a project, reducing the time required to coordinate various aspects of design and construction activities, reducing the time required to design an object, and reducing the duration of construction. (Table 1)

Table 1.

Key indicators for the duration of the investment and construction process

##	Name	Project duration indicators	Combining stages
1	Feasibility	Directive implementation period Return on capital	After making a decision on project implementation, the customer can start preliminary research
2	Pre-project stage	Specified directive project implementation period	Signing an investment agreement creates the legal basis for starting engineering surveys by the project organization
3	Design	Comparison of construction duration options for organizing construction	Combining interests design and construction organizations creates conditions for parallel production of works.
4	Construction	Setting construction deadlines according to the organizational and technological model	The use of advanced technologies and modern materials helps to reduce the construction time.

The duration of construction is part of the total life cycle of the investment project. However, this part is considered the most complex and subject to risk factors. First, technical and technological constraints determine the possibilities of using best practices and limiting the use of additional material and technical resources. Secondly, the organizational and economic conditions and uncertainty of construction production make the construction stage vulnerable to external negative factors. Third, along with the design stage, construction is a sphere of manifestation of the economic interests of many entities that are objectively participants in the investment and construction process.

Conclusion. Determining the optimal construction time is one of the most important incentive indicators for investment process participants. The use of advanced methods of production organization, the use of modern construction materials and mechanization tools, as well

as the introduction of new technologies for the production of works have a positive impact on the construction time and create conditions for their reduction.

The question arises: how to use the positive aspects of each of the construction organization methods? It is necessary to develop a mechanism for the optimal combination of powers and responsibilities in the investment and construction process. Currently, the problem of forming a construction cluster is widely covered in the scientific press. In our opinion, this should be justified not only based on the high efficiency of clusters in agriculture and industry, but also on a deep study of the organizational and economic interests of construction participants.

The use of industrial construction methods, modern efficient materials, and a reduction in the proportion of wet processes helps to reduce the time required for construction work. At the same time, the growing role of customers in the investment and construction process leads to the fact that construction deadlines are set not for technological reasons, but based on investment considerations and the need to return capital investments. Compliance with the requirements of investors and customers is possible only if they do not contradict the economic interests of other participants. Reform of relations between participants in the investment and construction process should comply with the principles of market-based approach, mutual recognition of interests, priority of common goals, equality of powers, and effective decision-making.

Compliance with these principles implies the widespread use of network and information models for the formation of the construction process. In addition, it is necessary to develop a mechanism for managing the investment and construction process based on continuous improvement of construction management methods.

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